

DAMAGE DETECTION OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES BY TAPPING SOUND ANALYSIS : A NEW NDE METHOD

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ABSTRACT

A NDE method, which detects defect inside composite structure by using numerically simulated tapping sound data as a reference data, was proposed. The tapping event and the mechanism of tapping sound generation were numerically modeled. The tapping event was formulated by using finite element method with dynamic contact algorithm. Tapping sound generated by the vibration of the surface of structure was solved by using boundary element method. In order to decide the existence of internal defect, a decision method based on the wavelet packet transform was proposed. To verify the proposed numerical procedures, experiment on a laminated composite structure was performed. Comparison with the experimental results shows the validity of present numerical procedures. And, a experiment for the damage detection using proposed method was also performed.

INTRODUCTION

Laminated composites have many advantages over metallic material, and are widely used on aircraft structures. Delamination or disbond may occur inside laminated composite structure during operation or manufacturing. Because these defects are hardly detected by the naked eye, some systematic inspection methods are needed.

To detect the defects inside structures, nondestructive evaluation techniques are widely used for inspection systems. However, most of NDE techniques are not only expensive but also extremely cumbersome for field application.

On the other hand, experienced inspectors can detect defects by using the coin tap test. The coin tap test requires the inspectors to tap with a coin-like object on the surface of structure to be inspected, feeling the subtle difference of contact force and/or hearing the tapping sound to determine the existence of internal defects. Concerning about the coin tap test, Cawley et al.[1] examined the performance and sensitivity of the coin tap method by numerical simulations and experiments. They used the contact duration and magnitude of the contact force as the references to detect the existence of internal defects of thin aluminum beam specimens. Recently, Computer Aided Tap Tester was devised and tested for the detection of defects in the composite structures of aircraft [2]. Computer

Aided Tap Tester uses the contact duration change as the criterion of damage detection. In contrast to the method using contact duration, Pfund [3] argued that in the complex real world environment, with surfaces in arbitrary orientations and states of surface contamination, the sound, propagated through air, is the best indicator of subsurface conditions.

Although the result of coin tap test is subjective, the coin tap test is a cost-effective method and is used successfully in the field of detection of delamination of laminated composites or honeycomb sandwich. In the case of complex and irregular structure, the defective region is discriminated by comparing the tap test result of the structure to be inspected with that of undamaged structure. For the comparison of tap test result, the reference data is needed. If the structural parts are mass-produced, the reference data can be obtained by measuring the tap test result of several samples. However, the structural parts are not mass-produced, it is impossible to get sufficient samples. And even though the parts are mass-produced, the objectivity and absoluteness of the reference data cannot be guaranteed if the flawlessness of undamaged structural part is not guaranteed. Therefore, a objective and absolute way to obtain the reference data is required.

On these backgrounds, this work proposed a procedure of numerical simulation to obtain objective and absolute reference data of coin tap test. The tapping event and the mechanism of tapping sound generation were numerically modeled. Using the proposed numerical simulation procedure, contact force and tapping sound of laminated composite structure were calculated. To ensure the validity of proposed numerical procedure, experimental verification was performed. Here, a new coin tap test using the numerically simulated reference data was proposed and named Tapping Sound Analysis (TSA). The distinguishing mark of Tapping Sound Analysis is that the reference data for the determination of damage is obtained by using numerical simulation.

INTRODUCTION OF TAPPING SOUND ANALYSIS (TSA)

If subsurface defects have formed, the structural properties will be altered. The alteration of structural properties due to subsurface defects results in slight changes in the tapping sound. Tapping Sound Analysis finds defective region by comparing the tapping sound of the structure to be inspected with numerically simulated tapping sound of undamaged structure. Here, the numerically simulated tapping sound of undamaged structure is defined as the *sound print* of the structure. As a reference data, the sound print should be objective and absolute. For the precise calculation of the tapping sound data, a detailed modeling of the tapping event and the sound radiation is needed

In general, changes in the tapping sound are subtle and the results of damage detection by the coin tap test totally depends on the experience of inspectors. Therefore, Tapping Sound Analysis proposes a special decision technique. A decision by the direct comparison of tapping sound data is not efficient and sometimes may produce a wrong answer. As an efficient comparison method, feature data extracted from the tapping sound data should be used in the comparison process. Feature extraction is as important as the objectivity and preciseness of the sound print.

NUMERICAL MODELING OF TAPPING SOUND

The tapping sound generation mechanism is quite complicated. Numerical simulation of tapping sound consists of two parts: simulation of tapping force and vibration of the test structure, and simulation of the tapping sound radiated from the surface of the structure.

3.1 Simulation of tapping force and vibration of test structure

The tapping event can be modeled as an impact problem and treated by dynamic contact algorithm. The vibrating motion of structure is calculated using finite element method. The matrix form of the space-discretized equation of motion [4] can be obtained as

$$\mathbf{m}\mathbf{a} + \mathbf{c}\mathbf{v} + \mathbf{k}\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{f} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{m} is the mass matrix, \mathbf{c} is the damping matrix, \mathbf{k} is the stiffness matrix, \mathbf{f} is the external force vector and \mathbf{a} , \mathbf{v} , \mathbf{u} are the acceleration vector, the velocity vector and the displacement vector, respectively. The central difference method [4] was used as the time integration method in this paper. Substituting the assumption of \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{v} in equation (1), we obtain

$$\left(\frac{1}{\Delta t^2}\mathbf{m} + \frac{1}{\Delta t}\mathbf{c}\right)\mathbf{u}_{n+1} = \mathbf{f}_n - \left(\mathbf{k} - \frac{2}{\Delta t^2}\mathbf{m}\right)\mathbf{u}_n - \left(\frac{1}{\Delta t^2}\mathbf{m} - \frac{1}{2\Delta t}\mathbf{c}\right)\mathbf{u}_{n-1} \quad (5)$$

from which we can solve for \mathbf{u}_{n+1} . For the computational efficiency, mass matrix \mathbf{m} was diagonal lumped mass matrix. And damping matrix \mathbf{c} is also diagonal matrix made by multiplying mass matrix by a constant.

$$\mathbf{c} = \alpha \mathbf{m} \quad (6)$$

\mathbf{f}_n is the external force at the time of t_n . For the present problem, contact force between the tapping object and the test structure is the only external force. The contact force \mathbf{f}_n is calculated by using a dynamic contact algorithm based on the exterior penalty method.

3.2 Calculation of Tapping Sound

The governing equation of the sound field radiated from the vibrating surface can be analyzed using the following Helmholtz equation and boundary conditions [5].

$$\nabla^2 p + k^2 p = 0 \text{ in } \Omega(x), \quad (7)$$

where $k = \omega / c$ is the wave number and the boundary conditions are;

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial n_s} = -\rho_0 \dot{v}_n \text{ on } \partial\Omega(x) \quad (8)$$

In this study, BEM is used for the calculation of the radiated sound field. By introducing a fundamental solution, we can derive the following integral equation.

$$\int_{\Omega} (p \nabla_s^2 p^* - p^* \nabla_s^2 p) dV = - \int_{\partial\Omega} \left[p \frac{\partial p^*}{\partial n_s} - p^* \frac{\partial p}{\partial n_s} \right] dS \quad (11)$$

Using BEM, we can set a matrix equation on the surface $\partial\Omega$ as,

$$[A]\{P\} = [B]\left\{\frac{\partial P}{\partial n}\right\} \quad (15)$$

and

$$\left\{\frac{\partial P}{\partial n}\right\} = -\rho j \omega \{V_n\} = \rho \omega^2 \{U_n\} \quad (16)$$

where $\{V_n\}$ and $\{U_n\}$ are the normal velocity and displacement of fluid on the surface of the structure in the frequency domain, respectively.

Finally,

$$[A]\{P\} = [C]\{U_n\} \quad (17)$$

After calculating $\{P\}$ on the surface, pressure in the domain Ω can be obtained by equation (12).

In this case, equation (12) is solved in the domain Ω using BEM.

$$P = \{A'\}^T \{P\} + \{C'\}^T \{U_n\} \quad (18)$$

The sound pressure data in the time domain is calculated using the sound pressure data in the frequency domain using following equation,

$$p(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{l-1} P(n) e^{j t \omega(n)} \quad (19)$$

where, $p(n)$ is (n-1)'th calculated pressure value, $\omega(n)$ is (n-1)'th angular frequency of calculated value, and l is total number of calculated frequency.

DECISION METHOD USING FEATURE OF TAPPING SOUND

To determine the existence of defects by comparing the tapping sound, we need a method that pictures the characteristics of the tapping sound of undamaged structure and a test structure. Therefore, feature data, which reflects the characteristics of tapping sound data, should be extracted from the raw tapping sound data. After feature extraction, the feature data of the sound print (tapping sound of undamaged structure) and that of the tapping sound of the test structure are compared to find changes in the tapping sound due to the existence of subsurface defects.

4.1 Feature Extraction Method based on Wavelet Packet Transform

Wavelet packet transform [6] is used as the feature extraction scheme. After the wavelet packet transform, the energy of each packet is calculated [7]. The packet energy is defined as:

$$E_j^i = \sum_k^J P_{jk}^i \quad (20)$$

where E_j^i is the packet energy of the j -th packet in the i -th level, P_{jk}^i is the wavelet packet coefficient of the j -th packet in the i -th level, and J is the number of coefficients for that packet. And then, the array of packet energy having 2^i components is obtained. After obtaining packet energy array, the

packet energy array is normalized such that the norm of the packet energy array is equal to 1. The normalized packet energy array is defined as the feature array.

4.2 Deciding whether the structure is damaged or not

For the determination of existence of defect, the inner product of the two feature array vectors is defined as the *feature index*. Feature index is a positive real number less than or equal to 1. The meaning of the feature index is the degree of closeness of two feature array vectors. If feature index of a certain test point is close to 1, the tapping sound at that point is almost identical to the tapping sound of undamaged structure. Therefore, it is indicated that there is no damage near the test point. If feature index is less than 1, it is indicated that there is internal defect in the region of test point. By incorporating the idea of feature index, the decision of damage determination can be easily made even by the inspectors who do not have much experience. Moreover, the idea can be easily implemented in general digital computers for the artificial intelligence.

EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION OF NUMERICAL SIMULATION

Experimental verification of present numerical procedures was performed. The experimentally obtained tapping sound and simulated tapping sound were compared using proposed feature extraction method. And, finally, damage detection was performed using the simulated tapping sound data as the reference data

5.1 Manufacturing of the specimen and Experimental Setup

USN125BX (SK Chemical Co.) prepreg was used to make the laminate composite plates. The stacking sequence was $[0^{\circ}_5/90^{\circ}_5]_s$ and the size of plate was 15cm \times 15cm. Fig. 1 shows the experimental setup. The tapping was implemented by the pendulous motion of the impact hammer.

Fig. 2: Damage region and test points

The effective mass of impact hammer was 0.0588 kg and the measured tapping velocity was 0.1701 m/s. The contact force between the laminated composite plate and the impact hammer was measured using the force sensor in the head of impact hammer. The tapping sound was measured using microphone. Total recording time was 0.01 sec and 1024 samples per tapping were recorded both for the contact force and the tapping sound. Five test points were selected for the measurement of tapping sound and depicted in Fig. 2. The microphone was located 2 cm left of the center of the composite plate and 10 cm far from the surface of the composite plate.

5.2 Numerical simulation of Tapping Sound

For the finite element model, eight node solid elements were used to model the laminated composites. Because the flexural deflection was important in the present problem, incompatible mode[8] was incorporated in the finite element formulation. Each layer was modeled as one layer of finite element and 40×40 elements were used in each layer. 6400 elements ($40 \times 40 \times 4$) were used for the finite element analysis of laminated composite. Fig. 3 shows the finite element model of present numerical simulation. The boundary element mesh was the same

Fig. 3 Finite element model

as used in the finite element analysis. Four node quadrilateral elements were used and the total number of boundary elements was $40 \times 40 = 1600$. The tapping object was modeled as a rigid sphere. The mass of tapping object was 0.0588 kg and tapping velocity was 0.1701m/s. In the calculation of contact force by exterior penalty method, penalty parameter was set to be 2.5×10^6 . The time step of time integration was 1×10^{-7} sec. And damping parameter (α in Eq. 6) was set to be 150. Five test points shown in Fig. 2 were also used for the calculation of tapping sound.

5.3 Comparison of Experimental Results and Numerical Results

Fig. 4 shows the contact force time history of experiment and numerical simulation. The contact force time history of five test points are shown. The shapes of contact force time history are similar. Note that the contact duration times are almost identical. This fact is promising because Computer Aided Tap Tester devised by Hsu[2] uses contact duration time as the reference of damage detection. Therefore, present numerical procedures can be also used to make the reference data of the method using contact duration time.

Fig. 5 shows the tapping sound time history of experiment and numerical simulation. As shown in figures, the present numerical tapping sound is similar to that from experiment. As mentioned, the comparison of time history of tapping sound is very difficult. Therefore, the feature index was used to show the closeness of numerical results and experimental results. The feature indices using tapping sound of numerical simulation and that of experiment are shown in Table 1. In wavelet packet transform, 12th order Daubechies wavelet was used and the level of decomposition was 8. As in Table 2, the value of feature indices are close to 1. Therefore, it is stated that the present numerical procedures can make sound print of test structure successfully.

Table 1 : Closeness of tapping sound (Experiment vs. Simulation)

Test Point	1	2	3	4	5
Feature Index	0.8939	0.9384	0.8138	0.9475	0.9763

5.4 Damage Detection using Simulated Sound Print

Damage detection using simulated tapping sound data as the reference data was performed. A laminated composite structure having damage was manufactured. The size and stacking sequence are same as the undamaged laminated composite plate used in the verification of numerical tapping sound.

In this work, delamination was assumed for the damage inside structure. In order to produce delaminated region, a pillow insert consisting of Kapton tape around two layers of tissue paper was used to generate delamination. The size of delamination was 4.5cm ×4.5cm and placed in the middle of the laminated composite. Five test points shown in Fig. 2 were also used. Test point 1 and 2 were in the delaminated region and test point 3 was at the edge of delamination and test point 4 and 5 were out of the delaminated region. Using same experimental setup shown in Fig. 1, tapping sound of the laminated composite structure having a delaminated region was measured for each test point.

Table 2 shows the feature index for damage detection of present damaged structure. As shown in the table, feature indices in the delaminated region (test points 1, 2 and 3) shows that there is subsurface defect inside structure. Because test point 4 and 5 were out of the delaminated region, feature indices of these points are close to 1. According to the experimental results, tapping sound analysis which uses simulated tapping sound data as reference data can determine the subsurface defects inside laminated composite structure.

Table 2 : Dame detection using Tapping Sound Analysis

Test Point	1	2	3	4	5
Feature Index	0.8451	0.6646	0.6773	0.9115	0.9754

CONCLUSION

In this paper, a numerical procedures for the calculation of tapping sound was proposed in order to be used as the reference data for the NDE method. To simulate the tapping sound, finite element method and boundary element method were utilized. The tapping event was treated as an impact problem and solved by using a finite element method with dynamic contact algorithm. Radiated sound was calculated by using a boundary element method. In order to verify the numerical procedures, simulated tapping sound was compared with experimental results and agreed well with the experimental results. Damage detection of laminated composite structure was also performed. Tapping sound of a damaged structure was measured. The feature indices within the delaminated region were less than 1 and indicated the existence of inside defects.

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